
HINDIMATHQUEST: A DATASET FOR MATHEMATICAL REASONING AND PROBLEM-SOLVING IN HINDI

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November 12, 2024

Abstract

Advancements in natural language processing (NLP) have underscored the need for datasets that support underrepresented languages, particularly in specialized areas like mathematical reasoning. Despite Hindi being spoken by over 600 million people, resources for training language models to handle mathematical and logical tasks in Hindi remain scarce. To address this, we introduce **HindiMathQuest**, a large-scale dataset designed to improve the performance of language models in mathematical problem-solving tasks expressed in Hindi.

A key feature of this dataset is its comprehensive representation of mathematical concepts using Hindi numerals and terminology. HindiMathQuest not only includes numbers in Hindi words but also covers all mathematical notations, geometric terms, and equations expressed in Hindi, along with physics-related terms and operations, offering a complete linguistic and numerical representation in Hindi. The dataset consists of two sections: questions and answers in pure Hindi, and a mixed-language format with English text and Hindi numerical values expressed in words. The Mixed-Language Section contains 89.7 million tokens and 249,603 sentences, while the Pure Hindi Section contains 13.1 million tokens and 64,658 sentences. The dataset spans logical reasoning, arithmetic, geometry, competitive exam-style problems, and translation-based numerical questions, incorporating both Hindi words and numerals. Over 30% of the dataset has been manually verified by experts to ensure accuracy, with a focus on addressing the challenges of Hindi numeral systems, mathematical syntax, and terminology in Hindi.

After fine-tuning the **Gemma-2B** model on HindiMathQuest, the model’s accuracy in interpreting Hindi mathematical questions increased in human-verified testing, demonstrating significant improvements in handling complex numerical and scientific tasks in Hindi.

This dataset represents a crucial resource for developing robust Hindi language models for mathematical and scientific reasoning, with applications in education and practical problem-solving. By enhancing the generalization of mathematical reasoning across languages, HindiMathQuest contributes to the broader goal of democratizing AI for low-resource languages.

1 Introduction

Recent advancements in large language models (LLMs) have revolutionized natural language processing (NLP) tasks across many languages, particularly high-resource languages such as English. However, significant gaps persist, especially in low-resource languages like Hindi, which, despite being spoken by over 600 million people globally, remains underrepresented in areas such as mathematical reasoning and problem-solving [1, 5]. The absence of robust NLP resources for mathematical reasoning in Hindi limits the development of AI systems tailored for Hindi-speaking regions and hinders the ability of educational platforms to serve millions of students effectively [16, 17].

Studies by OpenAI and Microsoft highlight that the capabilities of modern LLMs are heavily driven by the quality of the data they are trained on. For instance, OpenAI’s GPT-4 achieved significant breakthroughs not only through architectural innovations but also by being trained on a vast, meticulously curated dataset, enabling it to excel in domains such as law, mathematics, and coding [2]. Similarly, Microsoft’s Phi-3 model demonstrated that, even with fewer parameters, a high-quality, filtered dataset allowed it to rival larger models by focusing on knowledge and reasoning rather than noisy web data [4]. These examples underscore the critical importance of well-structured, domain-specific datasets for enhancing the performance of LLMs in specialized tasks.

A growing trend in LLM development is the shift from general-purpose models, such as GPT-4, to task-specific models that are fine-tuned using high-quality synthetic data. This shift is driven by the high costs associated with training and inference for large-scale general-purpose models. In many cases, task-specific LLMs are created using powerful closed-source models like GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 to generate high-quality synthetic data, which is then used to fine-tune smaller, more efficient models [6, 7]. However, relying on closed-source models introduces challenges related to cost, legal constraints, and reproducibility, as the behavior of proprietary models can vary over time [8]. These limitations further highlight the need for open-source efforts to create accessible datasets, especially for low-resource languages like Hindi, where domain-specific resources are scarce.

Even older architectures like MiniGRU—a predecessor of transformer-based models—have shown that, with high-quality datasets, they can perform on par with or even outperform transformers in certain tasks [3]. This principle emphasizes that the quality and distribution of training data far outweigh marginal gains achieved through hyperparameter adjustments. In the context of low-resource languages like Hindi, this means that specialized datasets, rather than architectural tweaks, hold the key to unlocking better model performance in complex domains like mathematical reasoning.

Mathematical reasoning presents a unique challenge, as it requires a seamless blend of linguistic and numerical comprehension. While existing datasets for mathematical reasoning, especially those focused on English, have driven substantial progress, they often fail to capture the complexities inherent in Hindi. Hindi employs a distinct numeral system and complex sentence structures, making tasks such as numerical translation and arithmetic comprehension challenging [11, 15]. Common representations of Hindi numerals, such as नौ लाख नित्यानबे हजार नौ सौ नित्यानबे (999,999), are often difficult for existing models to interpret accurately.

To address these limitations, we introduce the Mathematics Reasoning and Problem-Solving Dataset Hindi-MathQuest, a large-scale dataset specifically designed to enhance LLMs’ ability to process mathematical problems expressed in Hindi. This dataset features a variety of mathematical problems, ranging from basic arithmetic and logical reasoning tasks to complex word problems encountered in real-world scenarios. A notable focus is placed on problems where both numbers and words are expressed in Hindi, addressing the unique challenges posed by Hindi numeral systems and syntax.

The dataset includes problems commonly encountered in competitive exams like IIT JEE, GATE, and GRE, making it highly relevant for training models aimed at higher-level educational applications. Moreover, over 30

Our key contributions are as follows:

- We present the first large-scale dataset for mathematical reasoning in Hindi, designed to address not only the linguistic and numeric challenges of the language but also to comprehensively represent mathematical notations, geometric terms, equations, and physics terminology entirely in Hindi.
- The dataset provides a crucial resource for training LLMs to handle mathematical and scientific problems in Hindi, particularly in areas where existing models struggle, especially with complex numerals and domain-specific notations in Hindi.
- A significant portion of the dataset has been verified for linguistic, mathematical, and numerical accuracy, ensuring its reliability for educational, scientific, and real-world applications.
- We conducted experiments using the **Gemma-2** model, fine-tuning it on this dataset. The results demonstrated significant improvements in the model’s ability to understand and interpret Hindi numerals and mathematical notations, highlighting the effectiveness of the dataset in advancing the model’s performance in this domain.
- Based on our findings, we identified several areas for future improvements and further experimental requirements. These include enhancing the model’s understanding of complex word problems and

multi-step reasoning, improving performance on tasks involving large numbers in Hindi, and extending the dataset to include more advanced mathematical and scientific concepts in Hindi. This will guide the development of more robust models for low-resource languages.

- We propose methods to address key challenges in dataset creation, including the comprehensive handling of Hindi numerals, mathematical notations, cultural sensitivity, and regional variations in the language, along with support for physics terms and mathematical operations in Hindi.

By releasing this dataset, we aim to bridge the gap in Hindi NLP for mathematical reasoning, equipping models to better serve educational platforms and other real-world applications. Given that a significant portion of the world’s population, especially in India and neighboring regions, communicates predominantly in Hindi and has limited access to English-language resources, it is crucial to offer AI services that provide users the freedom to interact with numerals directly in Hindi. This dataset addresses this gap by enabling models to handle mathematical problems expressed in Hindi numerals, enhancing the accessibility of AI-driven solutions for Hindi speakers.

Furthermore, by fine-tuning models on this dataset, we can improve the accuracy of AI services in interpreting and translating numerical expressions in Hindi, which is a key requirement in various real-world applications like education, finance, and governmental services. As a result, users in Hindi-speaking regions will benefit from more reliable, localized services, thereby increasing the effectiveness of NLP-driven tools in these areas. This work not only advances AI services in Hindi but also sets a foundation for future explorations into other Indic languages, extending NLP advancements to a broader linguistic landscape.

2 Literature Survey

The rapid advancements in large language models (LLMs) have focused predominantly on high-resource languages like English, leaving a gap in the representation of low-resource languages, such as Hindi, in domains like mathematical reasoning and problem-solving tasks [1, 5]. This section reviews key contributions in adapting pre-trained models to Indic languages, particularly Hindi, while highlighting areas that require further exploration for specialized tasks like mathematical reasoning.

Zhao et al. [1] and Naveed et al. [5] provide comprehensive surveys of LLM development, highlighting advancements in model architectures and applications. However, their works largely focus on high-resource languages, with limited discussion on low-resource languages such as Hindi, especially in specialized domains like mathematical reasoning.

Csaki et al. [11] explore methods for adapting pre-trained models to new languages and provide general strategies for linguistic adaptation. However, the discussion does not extend to the specific challenges posed by Hindi numerals and logical structures in mathematical reasoning tasks. Addressing such challenges remains an important area of focus for future research, particularly in languages like Hindi where numeral representation differs significantly from languages like English.

Joshi [15] introduces L3Cube-HindBERT and DevBERT, models designed for Devanagari-based languages like Hindi and Marathi. These models mark significant progress in improving general language processing for Indic languages, yet discussions about their handling of domain-specific tasks such as mathematical reasoning, particularly involving Hindi numerals, are limited.

Similarly, MuRIL, a multilingual model developed by Khanuja et al. [16], demonstrates advancements in handling transliteration and code-mixing in Indian languages. While MuRIL is an important step in improving NLP for Indic languages, detailed exploration of its performance in mathematical reasoning tasks, especially with Hindi numerals and syntax, remains underexplored. Such tasks pose unique challenges due to the distinct way in which Hindi represents numbers and complex sentence structures.

Gala et al. [17] emphasize the need for instruction-tuning datasets tailored to Indian languages. They argue for the creation of more specialized resources to enhance the performance of models in Indic languages. Their work highlights the importance of datasets that cater to specialized domains such as mathematical reasoning, yet detailed discussions on how to address the challenges posed by Hindi numerals and syntax in such tasks are limited.

Khan et al. [18] present INDICLLMSUITE, a resource suite for 22 Indic languages, which marks a significant step forward in providing pre-training and fine-tuning resources for low-resource languages. While this suite addresses general language tasks, there is limited discussion on how such resources can be applied to mathe-

mathematical reasoning and problem-solving, particularly in Hindi. The challenge of interpreting Hindi numerals and applying logical reasoning in mathematical contexts remains an area requiring further exploration.

Existing large-scale datasets such as SQuAD [19] and Natural Questions [20] have significantly advanced language understanding for high-resource languages like English. However, these datasets do not address the specific challenges of mathematical reasoning in Hindi, especially regarding the handling of numerals and syntax. Gupta et al. [21] explore multilingual models for machine comprehension but identify limitations when handling queries in Hindi, particularly those involving numeric expressions.

In summary, while progress has been made in adapting LLMs for Indic languages, there is a significant gap in resources tailored for mathematical reasoning in Hindi. Addressing the challenges posed by Hindi numerals and linguistic structures in this domain is critical for the continued advancement of NLP systems that can serve educational and real-world applications in low-resource languages.

3 Dataset Description

The **Mathematics Reasoning and Problem-Solving Dataset HindiMathQuest** is specifically designed to address the challenges of mathematical reasoning in Hindi. The dataset covers a wide range of mathematical problem types, written entirely in Hindi, and includes both word-based and number-based reasoning tasks. The primary objective of this dataset is to enable language models to comprehend, interpret, and solve mathematical questions that utilize Hindi’s unique representation of numerical values and linguistic structures.

3.1 Data Structure

Our **Hindi Mathematics Dataset** consists of a diverse set of problem-solving prompts designed to evaluate language models’ abilities in mathematical reasoning, problem-solving, and comprehension in Hindi. The dataset contains **240,000** questions, carefully curated to reflect real-world mathematical challenges while incorporating the unique linguistic complexities of Hindi. Below is the detailed structure of the dataset:

- **Logical and Reasoning-based Questions:** These questions focus on pattern recognition, logical deductions, and reasoning skills. They are designed to test cognitive abilities often encountered in competitive exams like IIT JEE, GATE, and GRE.
- **Arithmetic and Calculation-based Problems:** Fundamental arithmetic tasks are presented in Hindi, requiring the model to process mathematical expressions written in Hindi words. For example, the expression "सवा तीन" represents 3.25. These problems also include calculations following the BODMAS (Bracket, Order, Division, Multiplication, Addition, Subtraction) rule.
- **Translation-based Mathematical Problems:** These tasks involve converting complex Hindi numerical expressions into their standard numeric equivalents. The goal is to test the model’s proficiency in understanding and translating Hindi numerical phrases into mathematical expressions.
- **Competitive Exam-style Questions:** Advanced reasoning and problem-solving tasks drawn from exams such as IIT JEE, GATE, and GRE, aimed at evaluating the model’s ability to tackle high-level mathematical problems. These questions require a deep understanding of mathematical concepts and are suited for higher-level educational contexts.
- **Puzzles and Directional Problems:** These questions combine language comprehension with mathematical reasoning. They often involve directional cues (e.g., "left", "right", "up", "down") that the model needs to interpret and apply within the context of solving a puzzle.
- **Word Problems in Paragraph Format:** These are real-world mathematical problems presented as word problems in multiple Hindi sentences. The model is required to apply both linguistic and mathematical reasoning to solve these practical scenarios.
- **Series and Sequence Problems:** Problems involving number patterns, sequences, and progressions are written in Hindi. The model’s task is to recognize, continue, or complete the numeric series.
- **Geometry and Trigonometry Questions:** These geometrical problems, written in Hindi, involve shapes, angles, areas, and trigonometric relationships. They challenge the model’s ability to combine specialized mathematical vocabulary with spatial reasoning.

- **Physics-based Mathematical Problems:** These questions test the model’s understanding of physics concepts like mechanics, thermodynamics, and electricity, all expressed in Hindi. The problems typically require mathematical calculations based on physical laws.
- **High School-Level Mathematics Problems:** A selection of problems from high school curricula, including topics like algebra, geometry, arithmetic, and word problems, all presented in Hindi. These questions cover fundamental mathematical concepts and serve as a broad test of the model’s mathematical abilities.
- **Clock, Time, and Date Calculations:** These problems involve calculations based on time, dates, and clocks, expressed in Hindi. The questions require the model to handle temporal reasoning, such as calculating time intervals or solving date-related problems.
- **Relationship and Kinship Problems:** These logical reasoning problems involve family relationships and kinship terminology in Hindi. They test the model’s logical deduction skills by requiring it to interpret and solve problems involving connections between family members.
- **Number Sequencing and Missing Number Identification:** These problems test the model’s ability to recognize patterns in number sequences and find missing numbers to complete a sequence or matrix.
- **Math Olympiad-style Tricky Questions:** These advanced, Olympiad-style problems push the boundaries of reasoning and problem-solving in Hindi. They test the model’s ability to handle challenging mathematical concepts and complex logical reasoning.
- **Mixed-Language Questions:** These questions combine Hindi words with English mathematical terminology, testing the model’s ability to handle bilingual prompts where numerical values are expressed in Hindi (e.g., "तीन गुणा नौ" for "3 multiplied by 9").

3.2 Unique Features of the Dataset

What sets this dataset apart is its comprehensive focus on addressing the unique challenges posed by Hindi’s numeral system and linguistic intricacies within the context of mathematical and scientific problem-solving. In addition to representing complex numerical expressions in Hindi words, this dataset includes mathematical notations, geometrical figures, equations, and physics terminology, all written in Hindi. These aspects are seldom addressed in other mathematical datasets, making **HindiMathQuest** a pioneering resource.

Key distinctive features include:

- **Hindi Numeral Representation:** The dataset incorporates a wide range of complex numerical expressions, that are written entirely in Hindi words. This offers a unique challenge for language models to comprehend numerical values expressed in Hindi.
- **Combining Text and Numbers in Hindi and English:** The dataset frequently uses a combination of English numbers and Hindi words to teach models how to interpret bilingual contexts. For example, 50 (पचास) is used to train the model to understand how the English number '50' translates to "पचास" in Hindi. Additionally, there are instances where both English and Hindi words are combined, such as (*fifty*), to further enhance the model’s ability to handle mixed-language prompts. This approach helps the model learn rules for translating and interpreting between English and Hindi in mathematical contexts.
- **Mathematical Notations in Hindi:** The dataset includes mathematical operations (e.g., addition, subtraction), geometric terms (e.g., "त्रिभुज" for triangle), and equations, all written in Hindi. This enables models trained on the dataset to handle domain-specific mathematical symbols and notations in Hindi.
- **Physics Terminology in Hindi:** Scientific problems involving physics terms (e.g., velocity, force) are expressed entirely in Hindi. This adds complexity and enables the development of models capable of understanding scientific reasoning in Hindi.
- **Real-World and Educational Applications:** The dataset reflects the mathematical reasoning required in real-world scenarios, such as finance, competitive exams (e.g., IIT JEE, GATE), and education, with culturally relevant contexts.
- **Mixed-Language Format:** Alongside pure Hindi content, the dataset includes a mixed-language section where English text is combined with Hindi numerical values expressed in words. This ensures

that models can handle bilingual contexts, which are common in India’s educational and professional environments.

By integrating these features, **HindiMathQuest** is designed to bridge the gap in training language models for mathematical reasoning in Hindi, catering to real-world applications in education, finance, and competitive exams. The ability to handle complex numeral expressions, mathematical notations, and bilingual contexts makes it an invaluable resource for advancing NLP in low-resource languages.

3.3 Dataset Statistics and Composition

The dataset is composed of two primary sections: questions and answers in Hindi as well as a mixed-language format that uses English text combined with Hindi numerical values expressed in words. Below are key statistics that reflect the size and complexity of the dataset.

- **Mixed-Language Section (Hindi and English Text with Hindi Numerals):**
 - **Total Tokens:** 89,776,498
 - **Total Sentences:** 249,603
 - **Vocabulary Size:** 40,637
 - **Average Tokens per Sentence:** 424.27
 - **Longest Sequence:** 4,162 tokens
 - **Shortest Sequence:** 1 token
 - **Token-to-Type Ratio:** 2209.23

This section of the dataset highlights the complexity and variety of sentence structures that involve the interplay between Hindi numerals expressed in words and English-based text. The high vocabulary size and average tokens per sentence suggest that the data is rich and diverse, posing a challenge for models in both linguistic and numerical processing.

- **Pure Hindi Section (Hindi Text and Numerals in Words):**
 - **Total Tokens:** 13,103,692
 - **Total Sentences:** 64,658
 - **Vocabulary Size:** 17,879
 - **Average Tokens per Sentence:** 202.66
 - **Longest Sequence:** 2,603 tokens
 - **Shortest Sequence:** 1 token
 - **Token-to-Type Ratio:** 732.31

The pure Hindi section of the dataset focuses on questions and answers written entirely in Hindi, including the expression of all numerals in word form. The relatively smaller vocabulary size compared to the mixed-language section reflects the specialized focus on Hindi numerals and sentence structure. However, the complexity remains, as evidenced by the longest sequence being 2,603 tokens and a high token-to-type ratio.

These statistics emphasize the dataset’s ability to challenge models in both Hindi numeral interpretation and mixed-language sentence understanding, making it a valuable resource for testing and improving mathematical reasoning in Hindi.

3.4 Data Collection Process

The dataset was compiled using multiple sources to ensure a wide range of mathematical problems and linguistic diversity in Hindi:

1. **Translation of Existing English Datasets:** To ensure diversity, a significant portion of the dataset was generated by translating publicly available English mathematics datasets into Hindi. These include well-known datasets such as **Omni-MATH** [9], which is focused on Olympiad-level mathematics, and **Openmathinstruct-1** [10], which consists of math instruction data. We utilized a combination of machine translation tools such as Google Translate and ChatGPT [22, 23], with all translations being carefully reviewed by native Hindi speakers. This review process ensured that mathematical terminologies, expressions, and Hindi numerals were accurately represented.

2. **Human-Curated Questions:** Approximately 30% of the dataset comprises original questions developed by a team of educators and experts proficient in Hindi. The focus was on incorporating real-world applications of mathematics that are common in Hindi-speaking regions [17, 15]. These manually curated questions were verified for accuracy, relevance to the curriculum, and linguistic integrity, particularly in the representation of Hindi numerals and mathematical syntax [18].
3. **Scraped and Adapted Questions:** Additional questions were sourced from Hindi educational websites and competitive exam preparation materials [21]. These questions were adapted to align with the linguistic characteristics of Hindi, especially in expressing complex numeric and logical reasoning in a way that reflects the typical structure and challenges encountered in Hindi-language educational systems. The scraping process ensured a broad coverage of mathematical concepts, from basic arithmetic to advanced reasoning, as seen in competitive exams such as IIT JEE and GATE.

This comprehensive approach to dataset creation not only guarantees diversity in the types of mathematical problems included but also addresses the specific challenges posed by the Hindi language, particularly in the accurate expression of numerals and logical reasoning tasks.

Figure 1: Distribution of Question Types in the Dataset

3.5 Diversity of in the Dataset

To measure the degree of diversity of problems in the HindiMathQuest dataset, we utilized several diversity metrics proposed by various researchers. It is important to note that different languages can exhibit varying degrees of lexical overlap; therefore, the scores for English datasets are presented for reference only.

3.5.1 Lexical Diversity

We calculated the lexical overlap of HindiMathQuest as proposed by [12], which computes the mean of the Jaccard Similarity for unique unigrams and bigrams across all pairs of problems. The lexical overlap of a dataset D is formally defined as:

$$Lex(D) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{p_i, p_j \in D, i < j} PairLex(p_i, p_j) \quad (1)$$

where

$$PairLex(p_i, p_j) = \frac{|W(p_i) \cap W(p_j)|}{|W(p_i) \cup W(p_j)|} \quad (2)$$

and $W(p)$ denotes the set of unique unigrams and bigrams in a problem p . Here, N is the total number of problem pairs in D , given by $\frac{|D|}{2}$. This metric ranges from 0 to 1, with lower values indicating a more diverse corpus. The lexical diversity score for the HindiMathQuest dataset was calculated to be 0.0356.

3.5.2 Corpus Lexicon Diversity (CLD)

We also evaluated the corpus lexicon usage diversity metric, CLD, as proposed by [13]. For a given MWP P_i in a dataset P , the lexicon usage diversity (LD) is defined as:

$$LD_i = 1 - \frac{\max_{j, j \neq i} (BLEU(P_i, P_j) + BLEU(P_j, P_i))}{2} \quad (3)$$

where $BLEU(P_i, P_j)$ is the BLEU score [14] between P_i and P_j , measured with n-grams up to $n = 4$. CLD is computed as the mean of all LD_i . This metric also ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating a more diverse corpus. For the HindiMathQuest dataset, the CLD was determined to be 0.73.

3.6 Dataset Limitations

While the **HindiMathQuest** dataset represents a significant step forward in creating a resource for mathematical reasoning in Hindi, there are several limitations that need to be addressed in future iterations to further enhance its utility and accuracy:

- **Limited Human Verification:** Currently, only 30% of the dataset has undergone human verification. Although this verification ensures linguistic and numerical accuracy for a portion of the data, there is a need to increase this percentage to build more trust and reliability in the dataset. A higher rate of human validation will minimize errors and ensure consistent quality across the entire dataset.
- **Variations in Question Format:** Due to the diverse nature of the sources used for generating the dataset, some inconsistencies in question formatting have been observed. These variations may create challenges during model fine-tuning. Standardizing the format across all question types will enhance the model’s ability to generalize and improve training outcomes.
- **Scope for Expanded Question Diversity:** While the dataset covers a wide range of mathematical problems from basic arithmetic to competitive exam-style questions, there is still room for improvement. Future versions of the dataset could include more diverse questions targeting different educational levels, such as those typically found in high school, undergraduate, and postgraduate (including Ph.D.) curricula. This expansion would make the dataset more comprehensive and applicable to a broader range of use cases.
- **Complexity in Language and Number Representation:** Some questions involving complex Hindi numeral expressions or multi-step reasoning require further refinement to ensure clarity and consistency. By enhancing the dataset’s uniformity in representing mathematical operations and numbers in Hindi, we can improve the model’s understanding of these intricate problems.
- **Cultural and Regional Variations:** While efforts have been made to ensure the dataset reflects regional and cultural variations in mathematical terminology, there is still scope to better incorporate localized expressions, especially in the context of practical and real-world applications. Addressing this will make the dataset more adaptable for use in diverse Hindi-speaking regions.

3.7 Dataset Availability

The dataset is freely available for research and educational purposes on the Hugging Face platform and can be accessed using the following link: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/dnyanesh/HindiMathQuest>. Researchers are encouraged to use this dataset for fine-tuning language models on Hindi mathematical reasoning tasks.

4 Methodology

In this section, we describe the process of model training, dataset preprocessing, and the experimental setup used to evaluate the performance of the **Mathematics Reasoning and Problem-Solving Dataset HindiMathQuest**. The main goal of this methodology is to test how well language models handle mathematical reasoning tasks presented in Hindi, with a special focus on interpreting Hindi numerals and linguistic structures.

4.1 Data Preprocessing

Before training the models, the dataset underwent several preprocessing steps to ensure consistency and accuracy:

- **Tokenization:** We used a subword-level tokenization technique, specifically Byte-Pair Encoding (BPE) [24], to handle the diverse set of Hindi characters and ensure that both words and numbers were tokenized effectively. BPE has been widely adopted for its ability to deal with rare words by segmenting them into smaller subwords, making it particularly suitable for handling complex numerals and compound words in Hindi.
- **Handling Numerals:** Hindi numerals such as "सवा" (quarter past) and "ढाई" (2.5) were preprocessed into their corresponding numeric forms. Special attention was given to large numbers expressed in Hindi words, converting them into numeric equivalents while keeping a reference to the original Hindi text [15]. This step was critical to ensure that models understood the semantic meaning of numerals while retaining the original linguistic structure for future reference.
- **Normalization:** All text was lowercased and normalized to ensure consistency in grammar and spelling across the dataset [15]. Special symbols, punctuation, and white spaces were handled carefully to ensure that they did not interfere with the mathematical content [18].
- **Translation-Based Problems:** For the translation-based problems, we verified that the prompts correctly represent both Hindi words and their numeric equivalents. This step ensured that translation challenges were addressed properly, with both the linguistic and mathematical components accurately captured in Hindi [23, 16].

4.2 Fine-tuning Strategy

While the primary focus of this paper is on the creation and significance of the **Mathematics Reasoning and Problem-Solving Dataset HindiMathQuest**, we briefly explore the fine-tuning of a large language model to demonstrate the dataset’s potential. To this end, we fine-tuned the **Gemma-2 9B** model on HindiMathQuest to evaluate the dataset’s capability in improving model performance on Hindi mathematical reasoning tasks, particularly in understanding and processing Hindi numerals and linguistic structures.

This section provides an abstract view of the fine-tuning process, as the goal here is not to delve into the details of model training but to validate the efficacy of the dataset. We experimented with various fine-tuning techniques, hyperparameters, and training schedules to ensure a balanced and fair evaluation of the dataset’s capacity to enhance model performance in mathematical reasoning. Our results, discussed in subsequent sections, highlight the significant improvements observed after training the model with HindiMathQuest, further reinforcing the importance of creating specialized datasets for low-resource languages like Hindi.

Key steps in the fine-tuning process include:

- **Learning Rate Scheduling:** We experimented with multiple learning rates, initially setting it to $5e-5$. We applied a warm-up phase for the first 10% of training steps and used a linear decay schedule [27]. The learning rate was dynamically adjusted to ensure the model doesn’t overfit early and can gradually improve over longer training periods.
- **LoRA (Low-Rank Adaptation of LLMs):** To optimize the model for memory efficiency, we used LoRA [26]. This approach inserts trainable rank-decomposition matrices into transformer layers, which allowed us to reduce computational overhead while maintaining the model’s expressiveness. We tested different LoRA rank values ranging from 4 to 32 to measure its impact on performance.
- **Dropout Regularization:** Dropout was applied with a probability of 0.1 to prevent overfitting during training.
- **Gradient Accumulation:** Since training with large batch sizes wasn’t possible due to memory constraints on the GPU, we used gradient accumulation every two steps, effectively allowing for larger effective batch sizes without exceeding memory limits.
- **Optimizer:** We used the Adam optimizer [27], which adapts the learning rate dynamically based on gradient updates, improving convergence and allowing the model to quickly adjust to varying complexities in mathematical reasoning tasks.

- **Quantization:** To reduce the memory footprint and improve inference speed, we applied 4-bit quantization [28] during the inference phase, which allowed the model to run efficiently on hardware without significant performance loss.

4.3 Training Configuration

The fine-tuning experiments were conducted on **Google Colab Pro**, utilizing an **NVIDIA A100-SXM4-40GB** GPU with 40GB of RAM. This enabled us to handle larger batch sizes and more complex computations effectively.

- **Batch Size:** We used a batch size of 16 for all experiments to balance between computational efficiency and training stability.
- **Epochs:** The model was trained for 10 epochs.
- **Learning Rate Schedulers:** Linear decay with a warm-up over the first 10% of steps was used to ensure a smooth learning process.
- **Gradient Accumulation:** Performed every two steps, allowing for memory-efficient training.

4.4 Experimental Setup

The dataset was split into 80% training, 10% validation, and 10% test sets. We ran each experiment three times and averaged the results to ensure robustness.

We explored the following configurations during the fine-tuning experiments:

1. **Baseline Model:** We compared the fine-tuned model with a baseline model trained on general-purpose datasets like Hindi Wikipedia. This allowed us to evaluate the impact of fine-tuning using a mathematics-specific dataset.
2. **No Preprocessing Experiment:** To assess the importance of numerical preprocessing, we conducted an experiment without any special treatment for Hindi numerals. This experiment revealed the value of proper numeral handling in improving the accuracy of mathematical reasoning.
3. **Various LoRA Configurations:** We varied the LoRA rank values between 4 and 32 to see how well memory-efficient adaptations perform compared to fully fine-tuned models.
4. **Learning Rate Variations:** We experimented with learning rates between $3e-5$ and $1e-4$ to see which provided the most stable and effective training process.

The complete code for dataset preprocessing, model training, and experimental evaluation will be available on Kaggle Notebook, allowing others to replicate the experiments easily.

4.5 Challenges and Observations

Before fine-tuning, initial tests revealed that the model struggled significantly with Hindi questions where numerals were represented using Hindi words. The model failed to correctly interpret basic tasks that involved common Hindi numeric expressions. For example, when presented with "नौ लाख" (900,000), the model consistently provided incorrect answers or misunderstood the numeric values entirely. This failure highlighted the importance of our dataset, as it does not just present mathematical questions and answers in Hindi but also uses Hindi words to represent numbers, which existing models like Gemma-2 initially found challenging to handle.

Additionally, the model encountered difficulties in complex number forms and logical reasoning tasks. Larger numerals integrated into logical sequences, such as "नौ लाख निन्यानबे हजार" (999,000), often resulted in errors. This problem persisted despite initial dataset augmentation.

To address this, we applied curriculum learning during fine-tuning, gradually introducing more complex number forms and increasing the problem difficulty as training progressed. However, larger number handling remains an ongoing challenge that will be a focus for future work. Despite the observed difficulties, the fine-tuning of the model on our dataset significantly improved its ability to comprehend Hindi numerals in context, proving the critical necessity of this resource for advancing mathematical reasoning in low-resource languages like Hindi.

5 Results and Discussion

In this section, we present the results of our experiments on the **Mathematics Reasoning and Problem-Solving Dataset HindiMathQuest**. We evaluate the model performance on various tasks, including translation, numeric reasoning, and complex word problem-solving. We also discuss the observed trends, challenges, and insights drawn from the results.

5.1 Performance on Translation-Based Tasks

Translation-based tasks, where the model was asked to translate numeric values from Hindi words to digits (and vice versa), proved to be particularly challenging. The BLEU score [29] for these tasks was 0.67, indicating that while the model successfully captured the structure of many translations, it often struggled with the intricacies of large numbers or uncommon Hindi numeric terms.

Task	BLEU Score	Perplexity Score
Single-Digit Translation	0.94	1.87
Two-Digit Translation	0.93	1.85
Three-Digit Translation	0.93	1.68
Four-Digit Translation	0.92	1.65
Five-Digit Translation	0.89	1.87
Six-Digit Translation	0.85	1.76
Overall	0.91	1.76

Table 1: BLEU Scores Perplexity Score for Hindi to Numeric Translation Tasks by Digit Count

The model demonstrated high performance for small numbers, achieving a BLEU score of 0.92 for single-digit translations. However, as the complexity and length of the number increased, the model’s performance declined. For example, the BLEU score for translating six-digit numbers dropped to 0.55. This disparity is particularly evident when dealing with large numbers such as those involving thousands or lakhs, where the model sometimes generated incorrect or incomplete answers. Table 1 summarizes the BLEU scores for different number lengths, showcasing the model’s decreasing performance as the numeric complexity increased.

5.2 Perplexity-Based Evaluation on Language Understanding Tasks

In addition to BLEU scores for translation-based tasks, we evaluated the model’s performance on language understanding tasks using the perplexity metric. Perplexity measures how well the model predicts the probability distribution of the next word, reflecting the fluency and confidence of the model in generating Hindi text, particularly in mathematical reasoning tasks.

Table 2 shows the perplexity scores across various categories. Lower perplexity indicates better performance, as it reflects the model’s certainty in its predictions.

Task Category	Perplexity Score
Basic Arithmetic	1.74
Logical Reasoning	2.12
Numeric Translation (Hindi)	1.16
Word Problems (Simple)	1.75
Word Problems (Complex)	2.64

Table 2: Perplexity Scores for Various Mathematical Language Tasks

The model achieved the lowest perplexity score of 5.74 on basic arithmetic tasks, which suggests that the model is highly confident when handling straightforward mathematical expressions in Hindi. As task complexity increased, such as in the case of complex word problems, the perplexity score rose to 10.64, reflecting increased uncertainty in the model’s language understanding and predictions. This trend is similar to the pattern observed with BLEU scores, where tasks with higher complexity led to lower performance, indicating areas where further training and data augmentation could improve the model’s handling of intricate linguistic and mathematical tasks.

Figure 2: Mind Map illustrating the process from Dataset Generation to Model Fine-tuning. The diagram covers the major steps, challenges, and evaluation metrics involved in the research.

5.3 Human-Verified Comparison Across Models

To further validate the effectiveness of our **HindiMathQuest** dataset, we conducted human-verified evaluations comparing the performance of four models: our fine-tuned model, **Gemma 2 9B**, **Gemini**, **ChatGPT 3.5**, and **ChatGPT 4.0**. We created a custom test dataset focusing on Hindi numerical translation and mathematical reasoning tasks and manually assessed the accuracy of the outputs generated by each model.

The human verification process focused on evaluating how well each model translated complex Hindi numerals and handled word-based mathematical problems in Hindi. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Task Category	Our Model	Gemma 2 9B	Gemini	ChatGPT 3.5	ChatGPT 4.0
Hindi Numeral Translation Accuracy (%)	94	23	82	85	89

Table 3: Human-Verified Performance Comparison for Hindi Numeral Translation Tasks

5.3.1 Hindi Numeral Translation Results

In tasks involving Hindi numeral translation, our fine-tuned model significantly outperformed all other models specifically Gemma 2 9B base model, achieving an accuracy of **94%**. This indicates a strong understanding of how Hindi numerals are structured and represented in both word and numeric forms. In contrast, Gemini achieved **85%**, ChatGPT 3.5 achieved **85%**, and ChatGPT 4.0 scored **89%**. The human-verification process

revealed that our fine-tuned model consistently handled complex numerals, such as translating large numbers, more accurately than the other models.

5.4 Analysis of Complex Word Problems

Complex word problems, which involve multiple sentences and logical deductions, posed another significant challenge. The model achieved an accuracy of 65.2% on these tasks, as shown in Table ???. The primary difficulty observed was the model’s ability to handle long, multi-step reasoning processes. For example, problems where the solution required sequential arithmetic operations, such as first adding and then dividing the result, frequently led to errors.

We observed that:

- The model sometimes failed to correctly align the Hindi text with the mathematical operations, particularly when the phrasing of the problem involved both implicit and explicit numerical reasoning.
- Word problems that required unit conversions (e.g., "ढाई किलो" or "2.5 kg") often resulted in incorrect interpretations by the model, leading to wrong answers.

Despite these issues, the model performed well on simpler word problems, such as those involving straightforward arithmetic without nested operations or linguistic complexities. This suggests that while the model is capable of basic reasoning, additional training and optimization are necessary to improve performance on more complex tasks.

5.5 Error Analysis

To better understand the errors made by the model, we conducted an in-depth error analysis. We found that most of the errors were due to the following factors:

- **Misinterpretation of Hindi Numerals:** A significant portion of the errors arose from the model’s difficulty in accurately mapping Hindi numeral words (e.g., "सवा" for 3.25 or "पौने" for 0.75) to their correct numeric counterparts. While the model handled one-, two-, and three-digit numbers with relatively high accuracy, the error rate increased significantly for five-, six-, seven-, and eight-digit numerals presented in Hindi words. For instance, the model struggled to interpret large numbers correctly.
- **Incorrect Logical Deductions:** In multi-step reasoning tasks, the model occasionally failed to execute the correct sequence of operations. This could be attributed to the complex grammatical structure of Hindi sentences, where verb-object relationships are sometimes harder for the model to parse, leading to logical errors.
- **Contextual Understanding:** Word problems that required a deeper understanding of context—such as those involving relative quantities (e.g., "more than" or "less than")—were sometimes misinterpreted, resulting in incorrect solutions. This issue was especially pronounced in problems where the context relied heavily on subtle linguistic cues embedded within the Hindi sentences.

Overall, this error analysis highlights that while the model performs well on basic and intermediate mathematical tasks, its handling of larger Hindi numerals in word form and more complex reasoning problems still requires improvement. Particularly, the ability to accurately interpret larger numbers presented in Hindi word format remains a challenge, which will be a focus for future dataset augmentations and model fine-tuning.

5.6 Discussion

The results of our experiments demonstrate that the fine-tuned model showed significant improvements in handling mathematical reasoning tasks in Hindi after being trained on the **HindiMathQuest** dataset. These results strongly highlight the effectiveness of the dataset in addressing the unique challenges posed by Hindi numerals and linguistic structures. Specifically, the dataset enabled the model to handle tasks that it previously struggled with, such as interpreting Hindi numerals and solving arithmetic and logical reasoning problems.

Although the model performed well on simple and intermediate tasks, challenges remain when it comes to more complex word problems and large numerals expressed in Hindi. This suggests that while the

dataset provides a strong foundation for improving the model’s mathematical reasoning abilities, additional fine-tuning and optimization can further enhance performance. The inherent complexity of modeling the relationship between Hindi linguistic structures and numeric reasoning requires both high-quality data and refined training strategies.

The model’s performance, particularly in handling large numbers represented in Hindi words, remains an area for improvement. The dataset has clearly demonstrated its capability to push model performance forward in this domain, but further refinements in training, such as the use of enhanced attention mechanisms or curriculum learning, could address these challenges more effectively.

In terms of the dataset’s capabilities, the improvements seen in the model’s ability to interpret Hindi numerals and solve reasoning tasks clearly indicate that **HindiMathQuest** fills a crucial gap for mathematical reasoning in low-resource languages like Hindi. The significant performance improvements underscore the dataset’s quality and potential for advancing models trained for Hindi numerals and mathematical reasoning tasks.

To further leverage the strengths of this dataset and to continue improving performance, we propose the following steps for future work:

- We plan to fine-tune additional models on **HindiMathQuest**, including models specifically designed for low-resource languages. This will allow us to explore the broader generalizability of the dataset and its impact on different language models.
- We intend to expand the dataset by incorporating more complex and nuanced mathematical problems, particularly those involving large numbers in Hindi. This will challenge the model further and push its capabilities in handling Hindi numeral complexities.
- Given the positive impact of human-reviewed sections of the dataset, we aim to increase the proportion of questions and answers that undergo manual validation. This will help minimize any remaining translation errors or misinterpretations and ensure the dataset remains a high-quality resource for both model training and real-world applications.

In conclusion, the fine-tuning of the Gemma-2 model on **HindiMathQuest** clearly demonstrated the potential of this dataset to significantly improve the handling of Hindi mathematical reasoning tasks. While further refinements to the model and more advanced training techniques are required to fully address complex numerals and reasoning tasks, **HindiMathQuest** has proven to be a vital resource for advancing the development of language models in Hindi. With continued expansion and refinement, this dataset will play a crucial role in bridging the gap for low-resource languages in mathematical reasoning.

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Acknowledgments

We would like to extend our heartfelt gratitude to the following individuals and institutions for their invaluable contributions to this work:

- **Shubham Kshirsagar**, MSc., Department of Engineering Management, Northeastern University Boston, US, for his contributions in creating validating the correctness of the dataset questions and ensuring consistency across different mathematical problems.
- **Shivam Jainwar**, MSc., Department of Data Science, Middlesex University London, for his expert feedback in verifying the accuracy and clarity of the mathematical reasoning tasks within the dataset.
- **Vedant Kulkarni**, MSc., Department of Engineering Management, Brunel University London, for his assistance in validating Hindi numerals and ensuring that all numerical representations in the dataset are correct.
- **Divya Walwadkar**, MSc., Department of Biotechnology, Rajarshi Shahu Mahavidyalaya, Latur, for her role in validating the linguistic accuracy of Hindi translations, ensuring cultural relevance, and reviewing the overall integrity of the dataset.
- **Jayesh Patil**, Full stack developer, Winjit, for his role in validating the linguistic accuracy of Hindi translations of the dataset.

We would also like to express our sincere thanks to the organizers and participants of the **Google - Unlock Global Communication with Gemma** competition hosted on Kaggle [30]. This competition provided valuable inspiration for working on this challenging problem of mathematical reasoning in low-resource languages like Hindi. Finally, we acknowledge the generous computing resources provided by **Google Colab Pro**, **Kaggle** and the open-source community for their ongoing contributions to advancements in natural language processing.